

Free Energy Changes vis-a-vis other Thermodynamic Parameters as a Measure of Stability—A solid Phase Study on Heat of Dissociation and Pressure-Composition Isothermals of β -picoline Complexes of Fluoborates of Some Transitional Metals. Part I.

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The heats of dissociation (ΔH) of β -picoline complexes of the fluoborates of Co, Ni, Zn and Cd were evaluated from measurements of dissociation pressures at various temperatures. ΔH values are not fully correlated with the stabilities of the complexes derived on the principle that one with the lowest number of ligands is the stablest.

A series of investigations have been oriented to determine which one of the thermodynamical quantities is more reliable and useful to correlate the stability of the comparable complexes. The present paper deals with the evaluation and applications of the data on heat of dissociation of β -picoline complexes of the fluoborates of Co, Ni, Zn and Cd.

EXPERIMENTAL

The complexes were prepared by dissolving the fluoborates in β -picoline and crystallising them from the solvent. The methods of analyses to establish formula were similar to those described earlier¹. Zinc and Cadmium were determined as quinaldinates². The composition agreed with the general formula $M(\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot 4\beta$ -picoline. The cobalt complex was light pink and was less hygroscopic than the corresponding α -picoline complex. The nickel complex consisted of blue crystals. It was the least hygroscopic amongst the picoline complexes prepared. The zinc and cadmium complexes were white crystalline and not so hygroscopic. These were not readily soluble in water and were insoluble in alcohol, acetone, benzene and nitrobenzene.

Pressure-composition isothermals : The heat of dissociation was evaluated from measurement of dissociation pressures at various temperatures. The apparatus used for the measurements of dissociation pressures and pressure-composition isothermals was of the type described by Ray and Sinha.³ For all the compounds of β -picoline, pressure-composition isothermals were determined at 80°. Below 80° the loss in β -picoline in successive stages

1. G. C. Bhattacharya and H. C. Das Gupta, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 655.
2. A. I. Vogel. A Text book of quantitative Inorganic Analysis. 3rd Ed., 1961, p. 355, 494.
3. R. C. Ray and P. C. Sinha, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1946, **44**, 790.

was too inappreciable for accurate measurements. The nature of the isothermal curves is shown in Fig. I.

During the stepwise dissociation, cobalt and nickel complexes showed distinct colour changes. In the highest picolinated form the cobalt complex was light pink which changed to red and then deep red in the subsequent dissociated forms of the complexes. The nickel complex changed from blue to green.

The latent heat of vaporization of pure β -picoline, also determined with the help of the same apparatus, agreed closely with the reported values 10.03 Kcal⁴ and 9.344 Kcal.⁵

According to the Clapeyron-Clausius equation the logarithm of pressure was plotted against reciprocal of absolute temperature and from the slope of the linear graphs, the heat of dissociation ΔH of the complex was calculated. The results are recorded in Table I.

4. D. P. Biddiscombe and others, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, Pt. 2, 1957.

5. E. F. G. Harrington and J. F. Martin, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1958, **44**, 158.

TABLE I

Heats of dissociation of β -picoline complexes

β -picoline complex of	Molar ratio of fluoroborate : picoline	ΔH (K.cal)/Mole of picoline
Co(BF ₄) ₂	1 : 4/3	16.71
	1 : 3/2	14.47
	1 : 2/-	14.65
Ni(BF ₄) ₂	1 : 4/3	14.81
	1 : 3/2	14.76
Zn(BF ₄) ₂	1 : 4/3	12.29
	1 : 3/2	12.35
	1 : 2/-	14.33
Cd(BF ₄) ₂	1 : 4/3	15.95
	1 : 3/2	20.16
	1 : 2/-	16.84

DISCUSSION

Heat of dissociation has been extensively employed as a measure of stability of complex compounds. Heat of dissociation measures in effect whether a particular bond is either weak or strong⁶. It has been observed⁷ in the case of complex amines that the stability of the complex having the lowest ammoniated number of ammonia molecule is the greatest and has also got the highest ΔH value. Similar results were reported in case of complexes containing heterocyclic bases as ligands by Ray and Sinha⁸, and Mitra and Sinha⁹. The theoretical background of these findings are provided by Bjerrum^{10,11}.

The present investigation has shown that ΔH values cannot show or explain that order of stability in all cases of co-ordinated compounds. The convincing nature of ΔH , showing highest value for the lowest picolated compounds, is marked only in the systems with zinc; in other namely Co, Ni, Cd, the ΔH values fail to explain the stability of the lowest form of the systems. The ΔH values for 4/3, 3/2, 2 systems for cobalt come to 16.70, 14.56, 14.64 respectively whereas for 4/3, 3/2, 2 systems for cadmium come to 15.94, 20.15, 16.83 respectively. This sort of anomalous behaviour with respect to ΔH values is marked

6. A. R. Burkin, *Quart. Review*, 1951, p. 5.
7. W. Blitz, *et al.* 2, *Amery Chem.* 1919, **109**, 89; 1923, **129**, 1, 14.
8. R. C. Ray and P. C. Sinha, (*Coc. cit.*).
9. N. G. Mitra and P. C. Sinha, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **27**.
10. N. Bjerrum, *Chemical Review*, 1950, **46**, 381.
11. Chemistry of the Co-ordination compounds edited by J. C. Bailor, p. 140. Reinhold Publishing Corporation, New York, 1956.

in nickel systems also. The present studies showed that the above principle of Bjerrum is not followed. Hence ΔH in the case of the picoline complexes of fluoborates is a poor measure of stability. Similar anomalies were also reported by Bhattacharya and Sinha¹², Davies *et al.*¹³, Das Gupta and Bhattacharya¹⁴ and Bhattacharya and Das Gupta¹⁵.

A further study with γ -picoline complexes of Co, Ni, Zn, Cd fluoborates corroborated that in all cases the order of stability does not agree with ΔH values. In this context it will be of interest to find out whether other thermodynamic quantities can be utilised to measure stability of these complexes.

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13. T. L. Davis *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 1934, **56**.
14. H. C. Das Gupta and G. C. Bhattacharya, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 10.
15. G. C. Bhattacharya and H. C. Das Gupta, *Ind. J. Chem.* 1963, **1**, 14.